

SUPPLEMENTARY RELATIONS BETWEEN THE PROTEINS OF PULSES AND THOSE OF MILK BY THE BALANCE-SHEET AND GROWTH METHODS.

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Appreciable supplementary relation was found between the proteins of each of the pulses, *e. g.*, lentil (*Lens esculenta*) green gram (*Phaseolus mungo*), khesari (*Lathyrus sativa*), soya bean (*Glycine hispida*) and field pea (*Pisum sativa*) and those of milk, by the balance-sheet and growth methods, at 5 per cent level of protein intake, in the ratio, pulse proteins : milk proteins = 4 : 1 in the case of balance-sheet method and at 10 per cent level of intake, in the ratio, pulse proteins : milk proteins = 9 : 1, in the case of growth method. The condition of rats on mixed diets containing pulse and milk was better than the condition of those kept on pure pulse diets.

Pulses form a very important source of the proteins of the Indian dietaries. Investigations on the nutritive values of pulses carried out in this laboratory show that though they contain a high percentage of protein, the biological values are not very high (Basu *et al.*, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1936, **23**, 789, 881 ; 1937, **24**, 1001). Some of the pulses like lentil and *Lathyrus sativa* induce little or no growth in young rats. Previous investigations from this laboratory have shown that rice (Basu and Basak, *ibid.*, 1937, **24**, 1043) and fish proteins (Basu and De, *ibid.*, 1938, **26**, 177) have marked supplementary effect on pulse proteins. Sherman (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, **41**, 97) and Sherman and Winters (*ibid.*, 1918, **35**, 301) worked on human objects and found that small amount of milk proteins has marked supplementary effect on cereal proteins. Mitchell (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, **58**, 923) using rats, observed marked supplementary relations between corn and milk proteins in the proportion of 3:1 at a 10% level of intake. In the present paper the supplementary effect of the small additions of milk on the quality of pulse proteins has been investigated by the balance-sheet and growth methods. India is a poor country and the majority of the Indians cannot afford large quantities of milk and for that reason we worked with pulse and milk proteins in the proportion of 4:1 at a 5% level of protein intake in the balance-sheet experiment and at 9:1 ratio at a 10% level of protein intake in the growth method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Five pulses, namely, lentil (*Lens esculenta*), green gram (*Phaseolus mungo*), *Lathyrus sativa*, soya bean (*Glycine hispida*), and field pea (*Pisum sativa*) were used in this investigation.

The milk powder was prepared by allowing the whole milk to dry in a large basin over a water-bath. The dried milk was kept in a vacuum desiccator for several days, then powdered in a mortar and kept in a vacuum desiccator and preserved in the refrigerator. Only small amounts of milk powder were prepared at a time and each sample was analysed before an experiment was made with it. On analysis it was found that the protein content of the milk powder varied from 22–24%, while the fat content varied from 26–34%. Before finding out the supplementary effect of milk on pulses, an experiment was carried out on rats with milk powder at 3% level of protein intake by the balance-sheet method and the biological value was found to be 93. Fixen and Jackson (1932), feeding rats with whole milk powder at 7% level, found 86 as the biological value. The lower value obtained by Fixen and Jackson is due to their working at a higher level of protein. That the biological value of a protein decreases with increase in protein concentration has been shown by Mitchell (*loc. cit.*) and by Basu and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) and also by Fixen. Experiments done by us with rations containing only 3% proteins from the milk powder failed to produce any growth in young rats. The composition of the unmixed diets is indicated in Table D₁ and that of the mixed diets in Table D₂.

TABLE D₁.*Composition of unmixed diets.*

Constituents of diets.	Milk powder.	Lentil.	Green gram.	<i>Lathyrus sativa</i> .	Soya bean.	Field pea.
	Percentage of protein (approx).					
	3%.	10%.	10%.	10%.	10%.	10%
Milk powder	75 g.
Lentil	...	264 g.
Green gram	263 g.
<i>Lathyrus sativa</i>	186 g.
Soya bean	146 g.	...
Field pea	222 g.
Chopped sugar	54	54	54	54	54	54
Ghee	51	72	72	72	47	72
Cod liver oil	12	12	12	12	12	12
Salt mixture	24	24	24	24	24	24
CaCO ₃	6	6	6	6	6	6
Corn starch	378	168	169	246	311	210

Experiments by the Balance-sheet Method.

Typical data obtained with 3% milk proteins and with mixtures of milk and lentil proteins in the ratio 1:4 at 5% level of protein intake are indicated in Tables I and II. Results obtained with other mixtures are summarised in Table III.

TABLE I.

Biological value of dried milk proteins at 3% level of intake.

(The figures of intake and output represent daily averages.)

Rat No.	Weight		Intake		Nitrogen		Food N
	Initial.	Final.	Food.	Nitrogen.	Faecal.	Metabolic.	in faeces.
Experiment with nitrogen-free ration							
328	226 g.	224.7 g.	8.1 g.	...	16.57 mg.	*2.05 mg.	...
329	219	213.2	7.7	...	15.95	*2.07	..
330	144	143.0	6.0	...	7.88	1.31	...
331	129	123.5	9.4	...	17.21	*1.83	...
332	119	115.4	8.8	...	15.90	*1.81	...
333	90	86.0	7.3	...	15.48	*2.12	...
Experiment with 3% milk protein.							
328	227	227.5	13.4	64.3 mg.	30.88	27.47	3.41 mg.
329	213	209.9	13.0	63.8	28.84	26.91	1.93
330	146	146.7	8.2	39.4	11.92	10.74	1.18
331	129	125.5	9.2	44.2	20.34	16.84	3.50
332	121	117.6	9.6	46.1	20.14	17.38	2.76
333	91	90.4	7.6	37.0	18.33	16.11	2.22
Rat No.	Absorbed food N.	Urinary N Total.	Endogenons.	Food N in urine.	Food N utilized.	Biological value (B.V.)	Mean B.V.
Experiment with nitrogen-free ration.							
328	44.60 mg.
329	28.59
330	37.69
331	38.06
332	30.00
333	32.51
Experiment with 3% milk protein.							
328	60.9 mg.	49.47 mg.	44.60	4.87	56.03	92	...
329	61.0	35.40	28.59	6.81	55.09	90	...
330	38.2	39.22	37.69	1.53	36.67	96	93
331	40.7	42.15	38.06	3.09	37.61	92	...
332	43.3	32.33	30.00	2.33	40.97	94	...
333	34.9	35.65	32.51	3.14	31.76	91	...

* per g. of food.

TABLE II.

Biological value of proteins of mixed diets containing lentil and milk protein in the ratio 4 : 1 at 5% level of intake.

(The figures of intake and output represent daily averages)

Rat No.	Weight		Intake		Nitrogen		Food N in faeces.	
	Initial.	Final.	Food.	N.	Faecal.	Metabolic.		
Experiment with nitrogen-free ration.								
286	314 g.	312·8 g.	13·1 g.	...	28·64 mg.	*2·19 mg.	...	
287	255	251·2	12·3	...	26·28	2·20	...	
288	221	218·5	7·5	...	13·07	*1·74	...	
289	162	160·2	7·2	...	14·76	*2·05	...	
290	145	142·4	6·8	...	11·83	*1·74	...	
291	126	125·3	5·9	...	11·26	*1·91	...	
Experiment with mixed diet containing 5% protein (lentil : milk protein = 4 : 1)								
286	316	316·0	13·6	109·3 mg.	40·99	29·73	11·26 mg.	
287	256	257·3	10·8	86·8	31·71	23·78	7·93	
288	219	219·7	11·7	92·0	30·41	20·39	10·02	
289	165	166·0	9·3	74·8	23·90	19·07	4·83	
290	145	145·8	9·0	73·5	22·71	15·66	7·05	
291	122	122·5	7·8	78·4	23·62	14·88	8·74	
Rat No.	Absorbed Food N.	Urinary N.		Food N		Biological value (B. V.)	Mean B. V.	Calc. B. V.
		Total.	Endogenous.	In urine.	Utilized.			
Experiment with nitrogen-free ration.								
286	53·28 mg.
287	55·79
288	45·15
289	49·03
290	34·62
291	29·72
Experiment with mixed diet containing 5% protein (Lentil : milk protein = 4 : 1)								
286	98·04 mg.	82·69 mg.	53·28	29·41 mg.	68·63 mg.	70		
287	78·87	77·00	55·79	22·21	56·66	72		
288	81·98	68·92	45·15	23·77	58·21	71	70	62
289	69·97	71·31	49·03	22·36	47·61	68		
290	66·45	55·25	34·62	20·63	45·82	69		
291	69·66	51·48	29·72	21·76	57·90	69		

* per g. of food.

TABLE III.

Biological value of mixed pulse and milk proteins (4:1) at 5% level.

Name of pulse	Observed value.	Calc. from individual values for pulse and milk.
<i>Lens esculenta</i> (lentil)	70	62
<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> (green gram)	74	70
<i>Lathyrus sativa</i> (khesari)	77	65
<i>Glycine hispida</i> (soya bean)	81	72
<i>Pisum sativa</i> (field pea)	69	63

Experiments by the Growth Method.

Typical growth data obtained with mixtures of *Lathyrus sativa* and milk proteins in the ratio 9 : 1 at 10% level of protein intake are indicated in Table IV. The results with all mixtures are summarised in Table V.

The values of growth per g. of protein intake with pulses alone and with mixtures of pulse and milk proteins (9 : 1) at 10% level are compared in Table VI.

TABLE IV.

Growth experiments with mixed proteins of L. sativa and milk in the ratio 9:1 at 10% level of protein intake.

F o u r w e e k s .							
Rat No.	Sex.	Initial wt.	Intake		Gain in wt.	* B. V.	Mean B.V.
			Food.	Protein.			
357	Male	55.0g g.	225.6 g.	22.56 g.	26.5 g.	1.2	1.1
358	Female	47.5	182.6	18.26	21.0	1.1	
359	Male	52.5	214.3	21.43	23.5	1.1	
360	Female	49.5	211.6	21.16	20.5	1.0	
361	Male	48.0	266.4	26.64	24.5	1.1	
362	Male	47.5	216.1	21.61	26.0	1.2	
E i g h t w e e k s .							
Rat No.	Intake		Gain in wt.	B.V.	Mean B.V.		
	Food.	Protein.					
357	423.8 g.	42.38 g.	34.0 g.	0.8			
358	398.4	39.84	25.5	0.6			
359	406.5	40.65	32.5	0.8	0.7		
360	425.3	42.53	22.0	0.5			
361	428.3	42.83	30.0	0.7			
362	468.8	46.88	33.5	0.7			

$$* \text{ B. V.} = \frac{\text{gain in weight}}{\text{protein intake}}$$

TABLE V.
Biological value of proteins of mixed diets containing pulse and milk proteins in the ratio pulse: milk 9:1 at 10% level of protein intake measured by the growth of young rats.

Source of protein.	Protein in the diet (per cent).	Number of rats.	Period of experiments (weeks)	Increase in weight.	Total food intake.	Protein intake (mean).	B.V.
				Variation. Mean.	Variation. Mean.		
Mixed proteins of lentil (<i>Lens esculenta</i>) + milk.	10 (Lentil : milk = 9 : 1)	6	4	22.0-27.5 g.	173.1-195.2 g.	186.1	1.3
				43.0-49.5	375.3-418.7	392.8	1.2
Lentil (<i>Lens esculenta</i>)	10	5	4	4.0-18.0	58.6-137.0	99.6	1.1
				5.0-18.5	115.2-236.0	182.3	0.6
Mixed proteins of green gram (<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>) + milk	10 (Green gram : milk = 9 : 1)	6	4	27.0-36.5	179.3-216.1	192.2	1.7
				58.5-66.0	468.7-457.7	442.7	1.4
Green gram (<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>)	10	5	4	12.0-22.5	98.0-159.5	123.0	1.5
				22.0-33.5	194.5-317.0	250.2	1.1
Mixed proteins of <i>Lathyrus sativa</i> + milk	10 (<i>Lathyrus sativa</i> : milk = 9 : 1)	6	4	20.5-26.5	182.6-266.4	219.4	1.1
				22.0-34.0	398.4-468.8	425.2	0.7
<i>Lathyrus sativa</i>	10	6	4	0.0-4.6	62.2-85.4	72.4	0.2
				0.0-10.4	103.2-168.3	127.3	0.3
Mixed proteins of soya bean (<i>Glycine hispida</i>) + milk	10 (Soya bean : milk = 9 : 1)	6	4	32.5-42.5	201.5-238.2	210.4	1.8
				59.5-74.0	457.7-571.4	520.3	1.3
Soya bean (<i>Glycine hispida</i>)	10	5	4	29.7-41.2	157.4-285.5	196.5	1.7
				57.0-70.8	362.6-522.4	441.6	1.3
Mixed proteins of field pea (<i>Pisum sativa</i>) + milk	10 (Field pea : milk = 9 : 1)	6	4	17.0-27.5	102.5-146.9	124.0	1.6
				24.5-32.0	204.1-244.8	222.8	1.2
Field pea (<i>Pisum sativa</i>)	10	6	4	15.7-20.0	120.0-135.9	123.7	1.4
				21.5-26.4	230.9-246.6	235.1	1.0

TABLE VI.

*Experiments by the growth method.**Growth per g. of protein intake with mixed diets containing pulse and milk proteins (9:1) at 10% level of protein intake.*

Name of pulse.	Growth per g. of protein.			
	Four weeks.		Eight weeks.	
	With pulse alone.	With pulse and milk.	With pulse alone.	With pulse and milk.
Lentil (<i>Lens esculenta</i>)	1.1	1.3	0.6	1.2
Green gram (<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>)	1.5	1.7	1.2	1.4
Khesari (<i>Lathyrus sativa</i>)	0.2	1.7	0.3	0.7
Soya bean (<i>Glycine hispida</i>)	1.7	1.8	1.3	1.3
Field pea (<i>Pisum sativa</i>)	1.4	1.6	1.0	1.2

DISCUSSION.

It will be evident from the above results that in each of the five pulses, when supplemented by milk at 5% level of protein intake and in the proportion, pulse proteins:milk proteins=4:1, the biological values, obtained by the balance-sheet experiment, are greater than the calculated values. Thus in the cases of *Lens esculenta*, *Phaseolus mungo*, *Lathyrus sativa*, soya bean, *Pisum sativa*, supplemented by milk, the corresponding observed and calculated biological values are 70 and 62, 74 and 70, 77 and 68, 81 and 72, and 69 and 63 respectively.

In growth experiments, the condition of rats on mixed diets was better than those on pure pulse diets; loss of hair was less apparent and the food intake and growth were greater with the mixed diets. With *Lathyrus sativa* and soya bean, the results are more interesting than others. The rats decreased in weight and showed loss of hair on a diet containing 10% proteins from *Lathyrus sativa* alone but when supplemented with milk this

pulse caused remarkably good growth in rats and very little loss of hair could be observed. In the case of soya bean, addition of milk caused little or no improvement in the condition of rats. The ratio $\frac{\text{gain in weight (g.)}}{\text{protein intake (g.)}}$ in the case of rats kept on mixed diet, containing soya bean and milk, was almost the same for those on purely soya bean diet. In other cases this ratio is greater in mixed diets.

Recently Aykroyd and Krishnan (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, **24**, 1093 ; **28**, 367) have obtained enhanced growth in hostel boys and also in rats by the addition of small amounts of dried skimmed milk to the typical Madras diet and they attribute the beneficial results obtained to the calcium content and some heat-stable factor in vitamin B₂ complex of the milk. The results obtained in the present investigation show that the beneficial results are partly due to the supplementary effect of milk proteins on pulse proteins. The daily addition of two proteins of very high quality, viz., lactalbumin and caseinogen, in the form of 1 oz of dry skimmed milk is also bound to have a beneficial effect on growth and general well-being.

The necessity of incorporating at least small amounts of milk in the Indian dietaries is thus obvious.

C O N C L U S I O N .

1. The biological value of proteins of whole milk at 3% level of protein intake is 93 by the balance-sheet method. With this ration, no growth in rats is obtained.

2. There is an appreciable supplementary relation by the balance sheet method, among the proteins of whole milk and proteins of each of the pulses, lentil, green gram, *lathyrus sativa*, soya bean and field pea at 5% level of intake, in the proportion pulse proteins : milk proteins = 4:1. The corresponding experimental and calculated biological values are 70 and 62, 74 and 70, 77 and 68, 81 and 72, and 69 and 63 respectively.

3. The growth per g. of protein intake is greater in the case of the mixed diets containing each of the above-mentioned pulses and milk, in the proportion, pulse proteins : milk proteins = 9:1, than the growth per g. of protein intake obtained from a pure pulse diet, in both the cases the level of protein intake being 10%. The only exception is soya bean where no supplementary effect can be found with milk, the growth per g. of protein

ingested being almost the same in the case of the mixed diet and pure soya bean diet.

4. Growth per g. of protein ingested for eight weeks of the mixed diet containing each of the five pulses, mentioned before, and milk, in the proportion of 9:1 at 10% protein level is as follows: lentil+milk, 1.2; green gram+milk, 1.4; *lathyrus sativa*+milk, 0.7; soya bean+milk, 1.3, and field pea+milk, 1.2. In the case of a pure pulse diet at the same concentration after eight weeks of feeding, the corresponding values are as follows: lentil, 0.6; green gram, 1.2; *lathyrus sativa*, 0.3; soya bean, 1.3, and field pea, 1.0.

5. The general condition of rats, kept on mixed diets mentioned above, is better than the condition those kept on the corresponding pure pulse diet. The loss of hair is less and the growth is greater in the former case.

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Received March 6, 1939.